
Job Satisfaction and Productivity of the Mabalacat City Government Employees

Carmelita Y. Ocampo

Ediric D. Gadia*

Imelda DP. Soriano

Institute of Graduate Studies

Gordon College

*Corresponding Author

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the job satisfaction and productivity levels of Mabalacat City LGU employees. The descriptive research included 170 employees. Key respondent profiles were as follows: 14.7% were aged 30-34, 57.1% were female, 54.7% were married, 63.5% were bachelor's degree holders, 11.2% were at Salary Grade 11, 43.5% were in administrative aide positions, 41.8% had 3-10 years of service, and 80.6% were regular employees. Factors contributing to job satisfaction included Physical Condition (mean: 3.22), Social Environment (mean: 3.34), Rewards and Recognition (mean: 2.80), Working Relationship (mean: 3.39), and Training and Development (mean: 2.98). Productivity measures showed high levels in Quality of Work (mean: 3.45), Efficiency of Work (mean: 3.52), and Innovativeness (mean: 3.36). Job satisfaction factors, such as Rewards and Recognition, and Training and Development, scored lower and need attention. The study concluded that age, educational attainment, salary grade, position, length of service, and appointment status did not significantly influence job satisfaction and productivity. Recommendations include enhancing job satisfaction, particularly in rewards and recognition, and developing programs to sustain high productivity levels. The LGU should create awards mechanisms and design training programs to empower employees. Future studies should replicate this research and explore additional variables to provide new insights into job satisfaction and productivity

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Job Productivity, Government employees, Mabalacat City

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INTRODUCTION

A lot of government agencies fail to understand the influence of working environment to the level of their employees' job satisfaction thus face a lot of difficulties during their work. Such organizations are internally weak therefore unable to introduce innovative products into the market to outshine their competitors (Aiken et al., 2002). The employees are the most important resources a company or an agency can have because they are the key players in the process of delivering services to the people. Employees should meet the performance criteria set the company or agency in order to optimize the achievement of their mission, vision and long-term goals. To meet the standards of the organization, employees must be placed in a working environment that allows them to work freely and creatively without problems that may hinder them from performing their maximum level of potential.

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In their study of job satisfaction and motivation, Herzberg et al. (1959) identified a number of attitudinal factors concerning job satisfaction and motivation. The motivators relate to the work itself and represent sources of satisfaction at work, such as achievement, recognition, work itself, responsibility, advancement and growth, whereas the hygiene factors relate to the work environment as potential sources of dissatisfaction, such as company policy and administration, supervision, salary, interpersonal relations, working conditions, status and security.

Many research papers have focused on the intrinsic aspect of the job satisfaction. Results have shown that there is a positive link between work environment and intrinsic aspect of the job satisfaction. Further they described the second dimension of job satisfaction known as context comprises of the physical working conditions and the social working conditions (Sousa-Poza & Sousa-Poza, 2000; Gazioglu & Tanselb, 2006; Skalli, et al., 2008).

Job satisfaction have been defined by many researchers and according to Scott et al., (2005) job satisfaction is defined as "any combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances that causes a person truthfully to say, 'I am satisfied with my job'". Another definition by Mosadeghrad et al., (2008) is that job satisfaction is the way of one behaving to perform their work in their job and organizations. As for Mosadeghrad et al., (2008) job satisfaction is "the extent to which people like or dislike their jobs". This idea will boost the work productivity of both the organization and among employees (Asio, 2021a).

Different factors within the working environment such as wages, working hours, autonomy given to employees, organizational structure and communication between employees and management may affect job satisfaction (Raziq & Maula-Bakhsh, 2014). In some organizations, it can be observed that mostly employees have problems with their supervisor who is not giving them the respect they deserve. Supervisors also show harsh behaviors to employees due to whom they are not comfortable to share good and innovative ideas with their supervisors. Furthermore, they described that top management limits employees to their tasks rather than creating a sense of responsibility in employees by making them work in teams to attain high performance. So based on this premise, employee engagement is an important ingredient in the organization (Mondejar & Asio, 2023).

Bakotic and Babic (2013) found that "for the workers who work under difficult working conditions, working condition is an important factor for job satisfaction, so workers under difficult working conditions are dissatisfied through this factor." To improve satisfaction of employees working under difficult working conditions, it is necessary for the management to improve the working conditions. If not, some employees will resort to procrastination due to dissatisfaction (Asio & Riego de Dios, 2021; Asio 2021). This will make them equally satisfied with those who work under normal working condition and in return overall performance will increase. Mondejar and Asio (2022) also emphasized that employees were satisfied with their supervisors, appropriate compensation, career plan opportunities among others.

For the past decades, the CSC has endeavored to build and maintain a responsive and responsible civil service through human resource systems that facilitate learning and development. Armed with its mandate "to establish a career service and adopt measures to promote morale, efficiency, integrity, responsiveness, progressiveness, and courtesy in the civil service, strengthen the merit and rewards system, integrate all human resource development programs for all levels and ranks, and institutionalize a management climate conducive to public accountability", the Commission has continuously introduced and adopted a host of programs, policies and measures to promote excellence in Human Resource Management (HRM) in the public service as observed by Mondejar and Asio (2022). For the past decades, the CSC has endeavored to build and maintain a responsive and responsible civil service through human resource systems that facilitate learning and development. Armed with its mandate "to establish a career service and adopt measures to promote morale, efficiency, integrity, responsiveness, progressiveness, and courtesy in the civil service,

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strengthen the merit and rewards system, integrate all human resource development programs for all levels and ranks, and institutionalize a management climate conducive to public accountability”, the Commission has continuously introduced and adopted a host of programs, policies and measures to promote excellence in Human Resource Management (HRM) in the public service.

The Civil Service Commission through the issuance of Memorandum Circular No. 3 series of 2012 urging all government agencies to come up with their own Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management (PRIME-HRM), thus the need for the Local Government Unit of Mabalacat City to come up with its Human Resource Development Plan that would help the Local Chief Executive, the City Human Resource Management Officer, the Human Resource Personnel and the city employees in general to have a guide or a plan for the professional development of its personnel.

Hypothesis

The following are the hypotheses of the study tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no insignificant influence of job satisfaction to productivity in terms of efficiency of work when grouped according to the profile of the variables.
2. There is no insignificant influence of job satisfaction to productivity in terms of quality of work when grouped according to the profile of the variables.
3. There is no insignificant influence of job satisfaction to productivity in terms of innovativeness when grouped according to the profile of the variables.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quantitative – descriptive type of research paradigm is used in this study with documentary analysis. In this study, questionnaires were utilized for this paper in order to collect the data from the Mabalacat City government employees to determine the influence of the employee’s job satisfaction vis-à-vis their productivity which used by the researcher in formulating Proposed Human Resource Development Plan. A quantitative approach is one in which the investigator primarily uses post positivist claims for developing knowledge, employs strategies of inquiry such as experiments and surveys, and collects data on predetermined instruments that yield statistical data (Creswell & Creswell 2017). This paper seeks to describe the present status of the identified variable which provides systematic information about the occurrence. This means that the quantitative researcher asks specific, narrow question and collects sample of numerical data from the participants to answer the questions. The researcher uses statistical method in analyzing the data. The researcher wishes that the number produced an impartial result that can be generalized to the larger number of public employees in the country.

For the purpose of this study, this describes the status and the conditions of the respondents who are the Mabalacat City government employees. Moreover, this describes the profile of the respondents in terms of: age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, and salary grade, and position, length of service and status of appointment. Similarly, this describes the factors contributing to job satisfaction namely: Physical condition; Social environment; Rewards and recognition; Working relationship; Training and development activities. Moreover, the factors contributing to productivity of the employees like Quality of Work; Efficiency and Innovativeness were also included.

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Respondents

The respondents of this study were the permanent employees of Mabalacat City included in their Plantilla of Permanent Employees and Casual Employees as of December 2017 with a total of four hundred and sixty-nine (469) city employees.

Table 1 show the number of respondents which will be involved in this study.

Offices	Total Employees per Department	Actual Respondents	Permanent	Casual
Office of the City Mayor	57	23	17	6
Office of the City Vice Mayor & Sangguniang Panlungsod Office	30	10	8	2
City Accounting Office	20	7	5	2
City Agriculture Office	22	8	6	2
City Assessor Office	20	7	5	2
City Budget and Management Office	20	7	5	2
City Building Official's Office	20	7	5	2
City Civil Registry Office	22	8	6	2
City Engineering Office	20	7	5	2
City General Services Office	22	8	6	2
City Human Resource Management Office	20	7	5	2
City Legal Office	20	7	5	2
City Planning and Development Office	20	7	5	2
City Social Welfare and Development Office	26	10	7	3
City Treasury Office	22	8	6	2
City Veterinary Office	20	7	5	2
Mabalacat City Birthing Station	24	9	6	3
City Health Office	22	8	6	2
City Environment and Natural Resources Office	20	7	4	3
City Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office	22	8	4	4
TOTAL	469	170	121	49

Instrumentation

The researcher formulated a questionnaire to be able to collect the data required in this study. The questionnaire contains the profile of the respondents in terms of: terms of: age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, salary grade, position, length of service and status of appointment. In addition, it also covers the measures of the factors contributing to job satisfaction namely: Physical condition; Social environment; Rewards and recognition; Working relationship; Training and development activities.

Items for the instrument were based on Approved Personnel Mechanisms of LGU – Mabalacat City that includes the Program on Awards and Incentives for Service Excellence (PRAISE) as per Civil Service Commission Resolution Number 010112 dated January 10, 2001, Annual Training and Development

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Programs of the city, Strategic Performance Management System as per Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 06 series of 2012 and the Program to Institutionalized Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management (PRIME HRM) as indicated by Civil Service Commission Resolution Number 1200241 dated February 01, 2012. It is consisting of three (3) parts namely: Profile of the Respondents inclusive of the Age; Sex; Marital Status; Highest Educational Attainment; Salary Grade; Position; Length of Service; and Status of Appointment. Part II is consisting of Factors contributing to Job Satisfaction: Physical Condition, Social Environment, Rewards and Recognition, Working Relationship, and Training and Development Activities. Part III includes Quality of Work, Efficiency of Work and Innovativeness.

Validation of the Instrument

A self-structured questionnaire was developed by the researcher in order to gather the data needed. Initially a draft was presented to the adviser for editing, revising and reviewing. After the first draft was completed, it was presented to the expert in the human resource field for another round of review, edit and recommendations on how the instrument could be improved. These experts have thorough knowledge of human resource management especially in the local government units. One is from the Civil Service Commission who is currently a Field Director in the province of Tarlac. The other validator is a former Field Director in the province of Bulacan and presently the Human Resource Management Officer of the Provincial Capitol of Pampanga. The third and last validator is the immediate supervisor of the researcher who has been in the government service for the last thirty (30) years and has been in the Human Resource Department of Mabalacat City for almost two (2) decades. A content validation form was signed by these three (3) experts in the field to determine its reliability and validity of the items indicated herein. All the suggestions relative to the study were considered in the finalization of the instrument. After the experts' validation, the instrument was finalized and was reproduced to multiple copies enough to be given to the prospective respondents.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were tabulated, organized and processed through Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 20 (SPSS v.20) respectively.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution were used to categorize the profile of the students- respondents which includes age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, and salary grade, and position, length of service and status of appointment. Weighted Mean was used to describe factors contributing to job satisfaction among the employees of Mabalacat City, specifically, physical condition, social environment, rewards and recognition, work relationship and training and development activities. The rating scale below was used for the interpretation of the results. Automatic Linear Modeling (ALM) was used to test if job satisfaction has a significant effect in the productivity of the LGU-Mabalacat City employees and when moderated according to their profile variables. The level of significance is 0.05.

Ethical Consideration

This study adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, ensuring compliance with ethical standards set by research ethics guidelines. Respondents/participants were fully informed about each step of the research process, with respect for their well-being being a top priority. Participation was entirely voluntary and posed no impact on their personal lives or those of their families. Confidentiality was strictly maintained, and no personal information was shared. The researcher recognized the importance of building trust with participants/respondents and carefully considered ethical implications throughout all interactions.

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Anonymity and confidentiality were guaranteed for all participants/respondents. Furthermore, all data collection materials will be securely stored and destroyed upon the study's completion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 to 9 present the profile of the respondents in terms of their age; sex; marital status; highest educational attainment; salary grade; position; length of service; and status of appointment.

Age. Understanding and intuition level are acquired by living and exposure to civil rights depending on its degree of learning experience through the years, their capability to exercise freedom in their workplace and the capacity to serve the people. Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents based on their age. It shows that out of the one hundred seventy (170) respondents, the dominant age bracket is 35 to 39 years old with twenty-nine (29) respondents, having 17.1% of the total population. However, there were only six (6) respondents or 3.5% in the bracket of 60 years old and above. This indicates that there are still living pioneers working in their own fields.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents when Grouped According to their Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
60 and above	6	3.5
55-59	15	8.8
50-54	22	12.9
40-44	22	12.9
35-39	29	17.1
30-34	25	14.7
25-29	19	11.2
20-24	9	5.3
Total	170	100.00

Sex. Distinction of sexes is determined to distinguish the capability of oneself to withstand their economic living status within their work field. Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents based on their sex. It shows that ninety-seven (97) or 57.1% of the total respondents were female while seventy-three (73) or 42.9% were male. Numerous behavioral studies have found women to be more trust-worthy and public-spirited than men. These results suggest that women should be particularly effective in promoting honest government." (Dollar, et.al, 2001). In addition, the government working hours is attractive and convenient for women particularly to those who have families.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents when Grouped According to their Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	97	57.1
Male	73	42.9
Total	170	100.00

Marital Status. Learning through experiences with regards to the marital status are of vital aspect depending on the degree of understanding and time management one possesses in their area of work field

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upon their service. Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents according to their marital status. This shows that ninety-three (93) or 54.7% of the total respondents were married while sixty-four (64) or 37.6% were still single. Four (4) or 2.4% of the respondents were legally separated while nine (9) or 5.3% were widowed. This indicates that most of the respondents are serving for their own families.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents when Grouped According to their Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Legally Separated	4	2.4
Married	93	54.7
Single	64	37.6
Widow	9	5.3
Total	170	100.00

Highest Educational Attainment. Continuous educational experiences are acquired and developed through the years to the extent of their understanding, inculcating the lessons they have had learned from their specific coursework to their own work places. Table 5 presents the grouping of respondents based on their highest educational attainment. This shows that one hundred eight (108) respondents or 63.5% of the total population have attained the bachelor's degree as their highest educational attainment while only one (1) or 0.6% attained the elementary graduate as the highest. This indicates that many of them strive to work in their own areas to serve the people and for their own families.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents when Grouped According to their Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Master's Degree with Doctorate Degree	8	4.7
Bachelor's Degree with Masters' Units	12	7.1
Bachelor's Degree	108	63.5
Associate Degree	9	5.3
High School Graduate	32	18.8
Elementary Graduate	1	.6
Total	170	100.00

Salary Grade. Monthly or annual salaries are determined depending on the relative position of the respondents in their respective institutions or companies. Table 6 presents the grouping of respondents according to their salary grade. This shows that thirty-four (34) or 20.0% of the total respondents have a salary grade of 1.00 while an equal number of one (1) respondent or 0.6% receives salary grades of 9.00 and 25.00, respectively. This indicates that many of the respondents receive the lowest salary while the other respondents were distributed among the high salary grades.

Level of Position. The level of position relies on the capability of the employee to withhold the load or weight of office work upon assessment or evaluation with respect to the existing policies for ranking or appointing. Table 7 presents the grouping of respondents based on their position. It shows that seventy-four (74) or 43.5% of the total respondents were Administrative Aides while fifty-three (53) or 31.2% are

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Administrative Assistants. Forty-one (41) or 24.1% of the respondents were in the position of Administrative Officer while only two (2) or 1.2% of them are in the position of Department Head. This indicates that many of the respondents attained the highest position among the four which determines their degree of learning experiences being developed through their own field of areas.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents when Grouped According to their Salary Grade

Salary Grade	Frequency	Percentage
25	1	.6
22	3	1.8
19	3	1.8
18	12	7.1
15	9	5.3
14	8	4.7
13	5	2.9
12	2	1.2
11	19	11.2
10	10	5.9
9	1	.6
8	12	7.1
7	7	4.1
6	7	4.1
4	15	8.8
3	11	6.5
2	11	6.5
1	34	20.0
Total	170	100.00

Table 7. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents when Grouped According to their Position

Position	Frequency	Percentage
Department Head	2	1.2
Administrative Officer	41	24.1
Administrative Assistant	53	31.2
Administrative Aide	74	43.5
Total	170	100.00

Length of Service. Efficiency and effectiveness in the profession are acquired through long years of experience/service, the degree of exposure in the field of area of work, and understanding their initiative while inculcating their mission, vision, and role toward the institution or company to serve the people and the community. Table 8 presents the grouping of respondents according to their length of service as employees in their field. It shows that seventy-one (71) or 41.8% of the total respondents have served for 3 to 10 years while only seven (7) or 4.1% of them have served for at least 31 years. This indicates that most of the respondents are in the developing process of their skills being acquired through the years while there are respondents who are trained and skilled enough to administer the institution or company they belong.

Table 8. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents when Grouped According to their Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
31 and above	7	4.1
21-30	24	14.1
11-20	25	14.7
3-10	71	41.8
Below 3 years	43	25.3
Total	170	100.00

Status of Appointment. Credibility and stability in administration are acquired and determined from varying levels of experiences and may depend on the appointment status of the employees. Table 9 presents the distribution of respondents according to their status of appointment. It clearly shows that regular status is the dominant, having one hundred thirty-seven (137) or 80.6% of the total population while thirty-three (33) respondents or 19.4% are of casual status of appointment. This indicates that the credibility and stability of administration of most employees are maintained in their own work fields. Lorenzo et al., (2021) also had similar findings in their study where most of their participants were regular government employees.

Table 9. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents when Grouped According to their Status of Appointment

Status of Appointment	Frequency	Percentage
Casual	33	19.4
Regular	137	80.6
Total	170	100.00

Factors Contributing to Job Satisfaction among the Mabalacat City Government Employees

Table 10 to 14 presents the factors contributing to job satisfaction among the employees of LGU-Mabalacat City in terms of Physical condition; Social environment; Rewards and recognition; Work relationship; and Training and development activities.

Physical Condition

It could be seen from the data presented in Table 10, the job satisfaction of the employees of Local Government Unit of Mabalacat City in terms of physical condition as determined on its prospective indicators. The data shows that five (5) indicators in the job satisfaction of the Mabalacat City government employees in terms of physical condition were rated “always”, including the statement which has the highest mean of 3.68 to wit: “appropriate working hours for employees”. This denotes that the employees are satisfied with the appropriate working hours being allocated to them in their job. It also reveals from the same data that five (5) items were rated “often”, including the statement which has the lowest mean of 2.64 to wit: “adequate personal space and storage (example: personal lockers, drawers)”. This denotes that personal space and storage of the employees were often given attention for the employees to work more diligently in their job. It can be implied that the employees of Mabalacat City government employees are often satisfied with the physical condition of their jobs as the data obtained an overall mean of 3.22 which indeed needs to be scrutinized enough for the betterment of their company or institution. According to the Public Service Health & Safety Association which is a Health & Safety Ontario Partner based in Canada, “a good work plays is an office which physical environment includes components of the tangible workplace

environment that comprise employee’s working conditions such as clean indoor air, safe drinking water, ergonomic workstation designs, violence and aggression-free work environment, available technologies, disability management practices, workplace policies and procedures, design and construction of the workplace.” Taghipour et al., (2015) also presents that environment which has noise pollution creates reactions which all indicate jeopardizing physical health such as severe headaches, stomach discomfort, unusual fatigue, lowered resistance against damage, extreme vulnerability against the cardiovascular disease. Work environment noise is also affecting mental health including impatience, irritability, stress, lack of concentration and difficulty. In work environment, noise pollution can threat workers and employee’s safety seriously. Also, high noise decreases concentration and obviously reduces job quality.

Table 10. Mean and Descriptive Rating of Respondent’s Job Satisfaction in terms of Physical Condition

Physical Condition	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Highly conducive and satisfactory work set up for job satisfaction.	3.42	Always
2. Office space and office equipment and supplies which are substantially enough.	2.92	Often
3. Appropriate working hours for employees.	3.68	Always
4. A work place with adequate lighting and ventilation.	3.39	Always
5. A work place which is safe and secured.	3.42	Always
6. Distance supervision for the responsible employees.	3.26	Always
7. Indoor air has good quality. (example: free from biological contaminants, low dusts level and low indoor carbon dioxide)	3.21	Often
8. Can work in privacy without noise or any other obstruction.	2.98	Often
9. Easy access in communicating with co-workers within the city hall. (Example: official communications via local lines, emails, etc.)	3.24	Often
10. Adequate personal space and storage. (example: personal lockers, drawers)	2.64	Often
Overall Mean	3.22	Often

Legend:

4	Always	3.25 - 4.00
3	Often	2.50 - 3.24
2	Seldom	1.75 - 2.49
1	Never	1.00 - 1.74

Social Environment

It could be seen from the data presented in Table 11, the job satisfaction of the employees of Local Government Unit of Mabalacat City in terms of social environment as determined on its prospective indicators. The data shows that eight (8) indicators in the job satisfaction of the employees of Mabalacat City government employees in terms of social environment were rated “always”, including the statement which has the highest mean of 3.48 to wit: “opportunities for good relationship with superiors; a presence of friendliness and brotherhood/sisterhood relations between superiors and subordinates”. This denotes that the employees show gratitude to their superiors so as to develop a sense of good relationship between and among them. It also reveals from the same data that two (2) items were rated “often”, including the statement which has the lowest mean of 2.95 to wit: “possibilities for fellowship, gathering and socialization

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during office breaks”. This denotes that the possibilities for social gatherings during office breaks are not attained due to having self-recreational activity or spending time with their own families. It can be implied that the employees of LGU-Mabalacat City are always satisfied with the social environment of their jobs as the data obtained an overall mean of 3.34 which ensures the effectiveness of socialization within the institutional environment. Cooperation in the workplace helps to create a supportive social environment. When people work together on projects rather than competing, they learn that their best interests are shared together, and that what benefits their co-workers also benefits them. Progressive corporate managers are aware of this fact and go to great lengths to foster teamwork amongst their employees. While some jobs will always be more efficiently done by individuals, a dominant culture of teamwork within a workplace helps to create a social environment that is conducive to good work, whether it is done in a team or individually.

Table 11. Mean and Descriptive Rating of Respondent’s Job Satisfaction in terms of Social Environment

Social Environment	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Opportunities for good relationships with peers; appreciation of the ways workers <u>interact</u> with me and vice-versa.	3.36	Always
2. Opportunities for good relationships with subordinates; subordinates are courteous, affectionate and helpful in their social and personal relations with superiors.	3.46	Always
3. Opportunities for good relationship with superiors; a presence of friendliness and brotherhood/sisterhood relations between superiors and subordinates.	3.48	Always
4. Feeling of being accepted by my peers, subordinates and/or superiors.	3.44	Always
5. Gets emotional support from peers, subordinates and/or superiors.	3.21	Often
6. Gets moral support from peers, subordinates and / or superiors.	3.31	Always
7. Possibilities for fellowship, gathering and socialization during office breaks.	2.95	Often
8. Able to establish good rapport with peers, subordinates and / or superiors.	3.32	Always
9. Easily adopts the norms and culture in the office.	3.47	Always
10. Cooperation and team spirit among office members are evident.	3.44	Always
Overall Mean	3.34	Always

Legend:

4	Always	3.25 - 4.00
3	Often	2.50 - 3.24
2	Seldom	1.75 - 2.49
1	Never	1.00 - 1.74

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Table 12. Mean and Descriptive Rating of Respondent’s Job Satisfaction in terms of Rewards and Recognition

Rewards and Recognition	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Acknowledgments earned for outstanding services.	2.92	Often
2. Acknowledgments earned for meritorious achievement, recognition and awards.	2.86	Often
3. Recognition for a job successfully done by employees.	2.95	Often
4. An avenue to participate in planning, organizing and evaluating plans.	3.00	Often
5. Incentive to recognize the worth of employees.	2.84	Often
6. Scholarships to outstanding employees to earn bachelor /masters/doctorate degrees.	2.43	Seldom
7. Consideration and recognition for the ability and success to accomplish a new task properly, efficiently, effectively, with ease and on time.	3.02	Often
8. Gets awards, plaques and or certificates / citations for successfully accomplishing a project / program.	2.63	Often
9. Cash incentives / (other than those mandated by law) for outstanding display of good values. (Example: returning of valuable items etc.)	2.53	Often
10. Gets chance to participate / join R & R activities on a yearly basis to recognize efficient and effective effort of the employees in the delivery of service to the public.	2.83	Often
Overall Mean	2.80	Often

Legend:

4	<i>Always</i>	<i>3.25 - 4.00</i>
3	<i>Often</i>	<i>2.50 - 3.24</i>
2	<i>Seldom</i>	<i>1.75 - 2.49</i>
1	<i>Never</i>	<i>1.00 - 1.74</i>

Rewards and Recognition

It could be seen from the data presented in Table 12, the job satisfaction of the employees of Local Government Unit of Mabalacat City in terms of rewards and recognition as determined on its prospective indicators. The data clearly shows that nine (9) indicators in the job satisfaction of the employees of Mabalacat City government employees in terms of rewards and recognition were rated “often”, including the statement which has the highest mean of 3.02 to wit: “consideration and recognition for the ability and success to accomplish a new task properly, efficiently, effectively, with ease and on time”. This denotes that there is not enough consideration and recognition within their office work even they have had accomplished their tasks properly and efficiently. It also reveals that one (1) item was rated “seldom”, with a mean of 2.43 to wit: “scholarships to outstanding employees to earn bachelor /masters/doctorate degrees”. This denotes that scholarships are seldom being given to the outstanding employees which may not be the priority concern of the management. It can be implied that the employees of Mabalacat City government employees are often satisfied with the rewards and recognition of their jobs as the data obtained an overall mean of 2.80 which determines that efforts of the employees are not that much noticed in their specific areas of work. Manzoor et al., (2021) pointed out that “providing extrinsic tangible rewards is generally seen as a reliable and effective way to encourage and motivate staff performance, as you can see, there are some consequences worth taking into account. While rewards can certainly provide short-term motivation and

drive, it generally does not drive long-term engagement, and must be continually invested in to make it succeed.” He also stresses that the following are the advantages of giving recognition to the employees; to wit: a) increases employees’ sense of competence and worth, resulting in increased pride and care in their work; builds meaningfulness and purpose for an employee, contributing to their job satisfaction as they recognize the relevance/importance of their role within the greater organization; and can be a great way to reinforce organizational values and cultures like improving teamwork.

Table 13. Mean and Descriptive Rating of Respondent’s Job Satisfaction in terms of Working Relationship

Working Relationship	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Can freely express opinions, solutions and feedback to projects and programs during meetings.	3.09	Often
2. Shares credit for accomplishments, ideas and contributions in the office.	3.18	Often
3. Compliments co-workers for their contribution in accomplishing tasks, projects or programs no matter how big or small their role might be.	3.31	Always
4. Practices common courtesy to subordinates / peers/ superiors. (<u>example</u> : Saying “Hello” or simple greetings)	3.61	Always
5. Willing to help subordinates / peers / superiors with their tasks even if it is not part of your work assignment.	3.58	Always
6. Feels comfortable working with co-workers.	3.57	Always
7. Highly motivated to report for work because of my officemates / co-workers.	3.39	Always
8. Communicates with courtesy to subordinates / peers / superiors.	3.56	Always
9. A democratic working climate.	3.29	Always
10. An atmosphere of interdependence between department heads and administrative staff, administrative assistant and administrative aides.	3.29	Always
Overall Mean	3.39	Always

Legend:

4	Always	3.25 - 4.00
3	Often	2.50 - 3.24
2	Seldom	1.75 - 2.49
1	Never	1.00 - 1.74

Working Relationship

It could be seen from the data presented in Table 13, the job satisfaction of the employees of Local Government Unit of Mabalacat City in terms of working relationship as determined on its prospective indicators. The data shows that eight (8) indicators in the job satisfaction of the employees of Mabalacat City government employees in terms of working relationship were rated “always”, including the statement which has the highest mean of 3.61 to wit: “practices common courtesy to subordinates / peers/ superiors (Example: Saying “Hello” or simple greetings)”. This denotes that the employees show enough courtesy with their co-employees as an expression of conduct in the institution. It also reveals that two (2) items were rated “often”, including the statement which has the lowest mean of 3.09 to wit: “can freely express opinions, solutions and feedback to projects and programs during meetings”. This denotes that certain internal policies are being implemented inside their work fields so as to maintain a good reputation within the institution but not by abiding their individual freedom of expression. It can be implied that the Mabalacat

City government employees are always satisfied with the working relationship in their jobs as the data obtained an overall mean of 3.39 which ensures the effective working relationships existing in their job. “The ability to understand people is one of the greatest assets anyone can have,” Bucero (2017). Understanding others takes time and effort, but it improves your ability to communicate with them. Good working relationships with your colleagues come from understanding how they think. Everyone has unique qualities. Appreciate the differences in the team. Celebrate each other’s approaches and outlooks and recognize that different cultures see things from a different perspective. Lastly, he pointed out that there is a need to develop personal empathy, and understand that their reactions are not always what you would expect.

Table 14. Mean and Descriptive Rating of Respondent’s Job Satisfaction in terms of Training and Development

Training and Development	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Able to attend in-house trainings, seminars and workshops related to the kind of work you do.	3.19	Often
2. Able to attend trainings, seminars and workshops conducted by National Government Agencies (NGAs) and/or Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) outside the province.	3.01	Often
3. Able to attend/participate in family day, sports fest or other activities sponsored and funded by LGU- Mabalacat City for the purpose of camaraderie of employees.	3.18	Often
4. Able to get financial assistance (in any amount) to pursue higher education.	2.24	Seldom
5. Receives regular coaching and mentoring from immediate supervisors / department heads.	3.00	Often
6. Gets adequate advice on career pathing and succession training.	2.92	Often
7. Able to get chance to job rotation and job enhancement.	2.81	Often
8. Gets opportunity to do challenging projects.	3.05	Often
9. Able to participate in the planning of activities, projects and programs of the office.	3.17	Often
10. Able to attend at least one (1) training, seminar and/or workshop to enhance work skills within the year.	3.25	Always
Overall Mean	2.98	Often

Legend:

4	Always	3.25 - 4.00
3	Often	2.50 - 3.24
2	Seldom	1.75 - 2.49
1	Never	1.00 - 1.74

Training and Development

It could be seen from the data presented in Table 14, the job satisfaction of the employees of Local Government Unit of Mabalacat City in terms of training and development as determined on its prospective indicators. The data shows that the respondents were “able to attend at least one (1) training, seminar and/or workshop to enhance work skills within the year”, having the highest mean of 3.25 and being rated as “always”. This denotes that the employees are eager to learn and extend their knowledge, skills, and understanding regarding their office work. It also reveals that the respondents were seldom “able to get financial assistance (in any amount) to pursue higher education”, which obtained the lowest mean of 2.24.

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This denotes that the respondents use their own personal earnings to pursue higher education. It can be implied that the employees of LGU-Mabalacat City are often satisfied with the training and development in their jobs as the data obtained an overall mean of 2.98 which describes that the employees need more trainings and development for their own careers. McNamara (2016), on his article, he pointed out general benefits from employee training and development and these reasons include: a) Increased job satisfaction and morale among employees; b) Increased employee motivation; c) Increased efficiencies in processes, resulting in financial gain, d) Increased capacity to adopt new technologies and methods, e) Increased innovation in strategies and products; f) Reduced employee turnover, g) Enhanced company image, e.g., conducting ethics training (not a good reason for ethics training); and Risk management, e.g., training about sexual harassment, diversity training.

Productivity among the Employees of Mabalacat City

Table 15 to 17 presents the productivity among the employees of LGU-Mabalacat City in terms of Quality of Work; Efficiency of Work; and Innovativeness.

Quality of Work

It could be seen from the data presented in Table 15, the productivity among the employees of Mabalacat City in terms of quality of work as determined on its prospective indicators. The data shows that the mean of 3.24 denotes that employee often “accomplish all the assigned tasks without revisions”. Having the highest mean of 3.59, the respondents always “show competence in delivering service to the clients/public”. It can be implied that the employees of LGU-Mabalacat City are always productive with the quality of work they exert onto their jobs as the data obtained an overall mean of 3.45 whereas being rated as “always”. According to Podsakoff et al., (1997) indicate that helping behavior and teamwork had significant effects on performance quantity and quality of work of the employees.

Table 15. Mean and Descriptive Rating of Respondent’s Productivity in terms of Quality of Work

Quality of Work	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Immediately determine solution to the clients / public concerns.	3.52	Always
2. Show competence in delivering service to the clients / public.	3.59	Always
3. Corrective action is observed to maintain the acceptability standards of work output.	3.44	Always
4. Accomplish all the assigned tasks without revisions.	3.24	Often
5. Has the ability to multi-task without sacrificing the quality of work.	3.46	Always
Overall Mean	3.45	Always

Legend:

4	Always	3.25 - 4.00
3	Often	2.50 - 3.24
2	Seldom	1.75 - 2.49
1	Never	1.00 - 1.74

Efficiency of Work

It could be seen from the data presented in Table 16, the productivity among the employees of Mabalacat City in terms of efficiency of work as determined on its prospective indicators. Having the highest mean of 3.63, the respondents always “act promptly on the request and attend to the needs of the clients / public”. As observed, it can be implied that the employees of LGU-Mabalacat City are always productive with the efficiency of work they exert onto their jobs as the data obtained an overall mean of 3.52 whereas being rated as “always”. In an article entitled “Seven Traits of an Efficient Employee” states that an “efficient employee always look to develop them professionally by working towards improving their position (Output Time, n.d.). They actively participate in their career development programs and also keep up on the current industry trends. Their efficient work pays off and helps them climb the organizational ladder. They are concerned about the company’s performance and also offer ideas to improve the same.” The employee performance will speak for itself. Not only is there a good performance with little supervision but also willingness to take up additional responsibilities. Such employees do not require supervision and direction to complete tasks. They take up the ownership towards their work and derive satisfaction by completing tasks and being productive.

Innovativeness

It could be seen from the data presented in Table 17, the productivity among the employees of Mabalacat City in terms of innovativeness as determined on its prospective indicators. The data shows that the mean of 3.21 denotes those employees often “identify areas where innovations may come in”. Having the highest mean of 3.52, the respondents always “integrate knowledge and skills at work in order to produce good results”. It can be implied that the employees of LGU-Mabalacat City are always innovative in their jobs as the data obtained an overall mean of 3.36 whereas being rated as “always”. A good employee and innovative is an asset to any organization as the key to the organization’s success is the effectiveness of the employees working in it. In such a scenario it is vital to pay importance to employee satisfaction. It is always necessary to address the fair needs of an employee and attend to his or her grievances to create job satisfaction, improve efficiency and a happy working environment. A happy employee is a productive employee and productivity is what contributes to the growth of any organization, (Fogaca & Junior, 2016).

Table 16. Mean and Descriptive Rating of Respondent’s Productivity in terms of Efficiency of Work

Efficiency of Work	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Able to prioritize tasks as to the level of urgency.	3.56	Always
2. Acts promptly on the request and attend to the needs of the clients / public.	3.63	Always
3. Receives good feedbacks as result of the work done.	3.34	Always
4. Find solutions to clients / public’s problem persistently.	3.52	Always
5. Finish all the assigned tasks within the target time.	3.55	Always
Overall Mean	3.52	Always

Legend:

4	Always	3.25 - 4.00
3	Often	2.50 - 3.24
2	Seldom	1.75 - 2.49
1	Never	1.00 - 1.74

Table 17. Mean and Descriptive Rating of Respondent’s Productivity in terms of Innovativeness

Innovativeness	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Integrate knowledge and skills at work in order to produce good results.	3.52	Always
2. Introduce new methods and techniques in doing one’s tasks.	3.30	Always
3. Make available different resources at hand for working out new ideas.	3.35	Always
4. Identify areas where innovations may come in.	3.21	Often
5. Initiate plan of action in dealing with tasks at hand to better satisfy the clients / public.	3.45	Always
Overall Mean	3.36	Always

Legend:

4	Always	3.25 - 4.00
3	Often	2.50 - 3.24
2	Seldom	1.75 - 2.49
1	Never	1.00 - 1.74

Significant Influence of Job Satisfaction and Productivity of the Mabalacat City Government Employees

Table 18 to 20 presents the significant influence of job satisfaction and productivity of the Mabalacat City government employees in terms of efficiency of work; quality of work; and innovativeness.

Efficiency of Work

Table 18 shows the influence of job satisfaction to productivity in terms of efficiency of work and the profile variables of the employee-respondents. These further shows that at alpha 0.05, job satisfaction insignificantly influences the productivity of Mabalacat City government employees in terms of efficiency of work and the following profile variables: age, highest educational attainment, salary grade, position, length of service, and status of appointment. Said profile variables do not affect the productivity of the employee-respondents in terms of efficiency of work. However, their job satisfaction significantly influences their productivity in terms of efficiency of work in the social environment and working relationship, and the following profile variables: sex and marital status. The t-values of 4.018 and 3.147 with corresponding probability values of 0.569 and 0.349 are significant at alpha 0.05 so as with the said profile variables with 31.5% and 32.0%, respectively. This means that productivity of the employee-respondents in terms of efficiency of work is effective and influential in the working relationship in their social environment. Also, sex and marital status patently affects the efficiency of work that employees exert onto their office work.

Table 18. Influence of Job Satisfaction to Productivity in terms of Efficiency of Work

Job Satisfaction	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P-value (≤ 0.05)	Importance (Effects)	Decision
Intercept	1.470	6.337	0.000	-	-
Social Environment	0.366	4.018	0.000	0.569	Significant
Working Relationship	0.312	3.147	0.002	0.349	Significant
F= 25.921 P<0.05 R ² = 31.5%	Model Equation = 1.470 + 0.366SE + 0.312WR				
Moderator (Profile Variables)	R ² (31.5%)			Decision	
Age	28.9%			Insignificant	
Sex	31.5%			Significant	
Marital Status	32.0%			Significant	
Highest Educational Attainment	28.8%			Insignificant	
Salary Grade	18.0%			Insignificant	
Position	21.3%			Insignificant	
Length of Service	27.5%			Insignificant	
Status of Appointment	28.3%			Insignificant	

Quality of Work

Table 19 shows the influence of job satisfaction to productivity in terms of quality of work and the profile variables of the employee-respondents. Furthermore, at alpha 0.05, job satisfaction insignificantly influences the productivity of Mabalacat City government employees in terms of quality of work and the following profile variables: sex, highest educational attainment, salary grade, position, and status of appointment. Said profile variables do not affect the productivity of the employee-respondents in terms of quality of work. However, their job satisfaction significantly influences their productivity in terms of quality of work in the social environment and physical condition, and the following profile variables: age, marital status, and length of service. The t-values of 5.064 and 2.963 with corresponding probability values of 0.745 and 0.255 are significant at alpha 0.05 so as with the said profile variables with 31.7%, 31.8%, and 31.0%, respectively. This means that productivity of the employee-respondents in terms of quality of work depends on the social environment and physical condition they currently work into and gained upon years of experience thus also affected by their age, marital status, and length of service.

Table 19. Influence of Job Satisfaction to Productivity in terms of Quality of Work

Job Satisfaction	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P-value (≤ 0.05)	Importance (Effects)	Decision
Intercept	1.477	6.405	0.000	-	-
Social Environment	0.367	5.064	0.000	0.745	Significant
Physical Condition	0.227	2.963	0.002	0.255	Significant
F= 37.950 P<0.05 R ² = 30.4%		Model Equation = 1.477 + 0.36SE + 0.227PC			
Moderator (Profile Variables)		R ² (30.4%)		Decision	
Age		31.7%		Significant	
Sex		29.5%		Insignificant	
Marital Status		31.8%		Significant	
Highest Educational Attainment		29.5%		Insignificant	
Salary Grade		23.3%		Insignificant	
Position		25.8%		Insignificant	
Length of Service		31.0%		Significant	
Status of Appointment		30.2%		Insignificant	

Innovativeness

Table 20 shows the influence of job satisfaction to productivity in terms of innovativeness and the profile variables of the employee-respondents. Job satisfaction insignificantly influences the productivity of Mabalacat City government employees in terms of innovativeness and the following profile variables: highest educational attainment, salary grade, position, length of service, and status of appointment. Said profile variables do not affect the productivity of the employee-respondents in terms of innovativeness.

However, their job satisfaction significantly influences their productivity in terms of innovativeness in the training and development, working relationship, social environment, rewards and recognition, and the following profile variables: age, sex, and marital status. The t-values of 2.963, 2.239, 2.100, and -2.015 with corresponding probability values of 0.340, 0.194, 0.171, and 0.157 are significant at alpha 0.05 so as with the said profile variables with 37.1%, 37.8%, and 37.2%, respectively. This means that productivity of the employee-respondents in terms of innovativeness depends on the training and development they have attended and internalized, working relationship they have acquired, social environment they belong, and the rewards and recognition they receive thus also affected by their age, sex, and marital status as skills and understanding are developed through various levels of experiences through the years.

Table 20. Table Influence of Job Satisfaction to Productivity in terms of Innovativeness

Job Satisfaction	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P-value (≤ 0.05)	Importance (Effects)	Decision
Intercept	0.831	3.081	0.002	-	-
Training and Development	0.252	2.963	0.003	0.340	Significant
Working Relationship	0.254	2.239	0.027	0.194	Significant
Social Environment	0.222	2.100	0.037	0.171	Significant
Rewards and Recognition	-0.142	-2.015	0.046	0.157	Significant
F= 20.394 P<0.05 R ² = 36.5%		Model Equation = 0.831 + 0.252TD + 0.254WR + 0.222SE - 0.142RR			
Moderator (Profile Variables)		R² (36.5%)		Decision	
Age		37.1%		Significant	
Sex		37.8%		Significant	
Marital Status		37.2%		Significant	
Highest Educational Attainment		34.2%		Insignificant	
Salary Grade		29.2%		Insignificant	
Position		32.2%		Insignificant	
Length of Service		35.7%		Insignificant	
Status of Appointment		36.2%		Insignificant	

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are the conclusions drawn from the findings of the study:

- 1) Rewards and Recognition and Training and Development as a factor contributory to the job satisfaction of the Mabalacat City government employees must be given consideration and importance considering that this two received the lowest mean rating and received “Often” as descriptive rating, respectively.
- 2) The Mabalacat City government employees are productive as to their quality of work, efficiency of work and innovativeness as reflected with the result and having a descriptive rating of “Always”.
- 3) On the Efficiency of Work - age, highest educational attainment, salary grade, position, length of service and status of appointment of the Mabalacat City government employees were not significantly influenced by their level of job satisfaction and productivity of the Mabalacat City government employees.
- 4) On the Quality of Work – sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, salary grade, position, and status of appointment of the Mabalacat City government employees were not significantly influenced by their level of job satisfaction and productivity of the Mabalacat City government employees.
- 5) On the Innovativeness - highest educational attainment, salary grade, position, length of service and status of appointment of the Mabalacat City government employees were not significantly influenced by their level of job satisfaction and productivity of the Mabalacat City government employees.

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On the basis of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

- 1) The Local Executive Council must do something in this regard so as to upgrade their level of job satisfaction especially on Rewards and Recognition and Training and Development.
- 2) A program must be developing to further sustain the high level of productivity of Mabalacat City government employees.
- 3) The grant of rewards and recognition must have an award mechanism to strengthen the job satisfaction of the employees of LGU-Mabalacat City.
- 4) For the LGU officials, to design a training and development programs to revitalize and to empower the Mabalacat City government employees to avoid the decline of their job satisfaction and productivity.
- 5) The study must be replicated to confirm or refute the result of the study, and that other researchers include other variables or indicators to contribute new ideas and insights in job satisfaction and productivity at work.

REFERENCES

- Aiken, L. H., Clarke, S. P., Sloane, D. M., Sochalski, J., & Silber, J. H. (2002). Hospital nurse staffing and patient mortality, nurse burnout, and job dissatisfaction. *JAMA*, 288(16), 1987–1993. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.288.16.1987>
- Asio, J. M. R. (2021). Determinants of work productivity among selected tertiary education employees: A PreCOVID-19 pandemic analysis. *International Journal of Didactical Studies*, 2(1), 101455. <https://doi.org/10.33902/IJODS.2021167470>
- Asio, J. M. R. (2021). Procrastination and Work Productivity of Academic Staff: Implications to the Institution. *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, 9(1), 46-53. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED613586>
- Asio, J.M.R., & Riego de Dios, E.E. (2021). Demographic profile and procrastination of employees: Relationships and determinants. *International Journal of Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences*, 7(1), 36-46. <https://dx.doi.org/10.20469/ijhss.7.20004-1>
- Bakotic, D., & Babic, T. (2013). Relationship between working conditions and job satisfaction: The case of Croatian shipbuilding company. *International journal of business and social science*, 4(2), 206-213. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=3261897>
- Bucero, A. (2017). Linking Organization's Strategy and Strategic Planning with Portfolio Management. In *Project Portfolio Management Strategies for Effective Organizational Operations* (pp. 61-80). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-2151-8.ch003>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- Dollar, D., Fisman, R., & Gatti, R. (2001). Are women really the “fairer” sex? Corruption and women in government. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 46(4), 423-429. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2681\(01\)00169-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2681(01)00169-X)
- Fogaça, N., & Junior, F. A. C. (2016). Is “happy worker” more productive. *Management Studies*, 4(4), 149-160. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17265/2328-2185/2016.04.002>
- Gazioglu, S. and Tansel, A. (2006) *Job Satisfaction in Britain: Individual and Job-Related Factors*. 9th Edition, Rutledge, Part of the Taylor and Francis Group, London.

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-
- Herzberg, F. (1959) *The Motivation to Work*. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- Lorenzo, E., Paguio, D., & Asio, J. M. R. (2021). Budget Allocation System of a Highly Urbanized Local Government Unit in Central Luzon, Philippines. *International Journal of Humanities, Management and Social Science*, 4(2), 51-62. <https://doi.org/10.36079/lamintang.ij-humass-0402.283>
- Manzoor, F., Wei, L., & Asif, M. (2021). Intrinsic rewards and employee's performance with the mediating mechanism of employee's motivation. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 563070. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.563070>
- Macnamara, J. R. (2016). *Organizational listening: The missing essential in public communication*. Peter Lang Publishing. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3726/978-1-4539-1739-8>
- Mondejar, H. C. U., & Asio, J. M. R. (2023). Employee Engagement Among Business Process Outsourcing Industries in a Freeport Zone Amidst the Pandemic. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 2(1), 13–26. <https://doi.org/10.31098/jsetp.v2i1.1662>
- Mondejar, H. C. U., & Asio, J. M. R. (2022). Human resource management practices and job satisfaction: Basis for development of a teacher retention framework. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(9), 1630-1641. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.03.09.04>
- Mosadeghrad, A. M., Ferlie, E., & Rosenberg, D. (2008). A study of the relationship between job satisfaction, organizational commitment and turnover intention among hospital employees. *Health services management research*, 21(4), 211-227. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=1693491>
- Output Time (n.d.). Seven traits of an efficient employee. <https://www.outputtime.com/seven-traits-of-an-efficient-employee/>
- Podsakoff, P. M., Ahearne, M., & MacKenzie, S. B. (1997). Organizational citizenship behavior and the quantity and quality of work group performance. *Journal of applied psychology*, 82(2), 262. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0021-9010.82.2.262>
- Raziq, A., & Maulabakhsh, R. (2015). Impact of working environment on job satisfaction. *Procedia economics and finance*, 23, 717-725. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)00524-9](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00524-9)
- Scott, M., Swortzel, K. A., & Taylor, W. N. (2005). The Relationships Between Selected Demographic Factors And The Level Of Job Satisfaction Of Extension Agents. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 46(3), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.5032/jae.2005.03002>
- Skalli, A., Theodossiou, I., & Vasileiou, E. (2008). Jobs as Lancaster goods: Facets of job satisfaction and overall job satisfaction. *The Journal of Socio-Economics*, 37(5), 1906-1920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2008.04.003>
- Sousa-Poza, A., & Sousa-Poza, A. A. (2000). Well-being at work: A cross-national analysis of the levels and determinants of job satisfaction. *The Journal of Socio-Economics*, 29(6), 517–538. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1053-5357\(00\)00085-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1053-5357(00)00085-8)
- Taghipour, M., Kheirhahan, H., Mahboobi, M., & Mohammadi, M. (2015). Evaluation of the relationship between occupational accidents and usage of personal protective equipment in an auto making unit. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 4(9), 9284-9259. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15680/IJIRSET.2015.0409141>
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